

Tris(quinolin-8-olato)ruthenium(III) complex : Synthesis, isomerization and, spectral and electrochemical properties

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Abstract : Reaction of a four-fold excess of quinolin-8-ol (HQ) with $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}_3]$ ($\text{trpy} = 2,2',2''\text{-terpyridine}$) in refluxing aqueous-ethanol in the presence of NEt_3 affords the facial isomer of tris(quinolin-8-olato)ruthenium(III) complex, viz. *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$, in which the quinolinolate ligands are coordinated to the metal center as a mono-anionic bidentate N,O-donors. Structure of the *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ complex has been determined by X-ray crystallography. This facial isomer of $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ complex can be quantitatively converted into the thermodynamically more stable meridional isomer by refluxing in *ortho*-xylene. The *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ complex is one-electron paramagnetic, and shows rhombic ESR spectrum at 77 K. It also shows a weak absorption in the near-infrared region and, intense absorptions in the visible and ultraviolet regions. Cyclic voltammetry on the *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ complex shows an irreversible oxidation at 1.11 V vs SCE and an irreversible reduction at -0.25 V vs SCE. DFT calculations have been carried out to explain the electronic spectral, as well as electrochemical observations.

Keywords : Quinolin-8-ol, ruthenium, tris-complex, facial isomer, crystal structure, spectral and electrochemical properties.

Introduction

The chemistry of ruthenium has been receiving considerable current attention¹, largely because of the interesting redox, photochemical and catalytic properties exhibited by the complexes of this metal. Ruthenium offers a wide range of oxidation states, which are stabilized by ligands of specific natures. For example, the relatively lower oxidation states are usually stabilized by π -acid ligands having soft donor atoms, such as carbonyl, polypyridines, phosphines, etc. Whereas the higher oxidation states require ligands with hard donor atoms, such as amines, carboxylic acids, phenols, etc., for their stabilization. In the present study, which has emerged from our continued interest in the chemistry of ruthenium having different coordination environments², we have selected quinolin-8-ol (abbreviated as HQ, where H stands for the dissociable phenolic proton) as the principal ligand. This ligand is known to bind to metal centers, via dissociation of the acidic proton, as a mono-anionic N,O-donor forming stable five-membered chelate ring (I)³.

Quinolin-8-ol has been particularly chosen as its two donor atoms are of opposite nature. While the pyridine-type nitrogen is soft, the phenolate oxygen is a recognized hard donor. Hence, chelation of a metal center by this ligand is always of special interest with regard to stability of the metal oxidation state. While studying the interaction of quinolin-8-ol with $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}_3]$ ($\text{trpy} = 2,2',2''\text{-terpyridine}$), taken as the ruthenium starting material, under different experimental conditions, we have accidentally discovered that reaction of a four-fold excess of quinolin-8-ol with $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}_3]$ in refluxing aqueous-ethanol in the presence of NEt_3 affords the facial isomer of tris-quinolinolate complex exclusively. Herein we describe the chemistry of this tris-complex of ruthenium, with special reference to its formation, structure, isomerization and, spectral and electrochemical properties.

Experimental

Materials :

Commercial ruthenium trichloride, purchased from Arora Matthey, Kolkata, India, was converted to $\text{RuCl}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ by repeated evaporation with concentrated hydrochloric acid. Quinolin-8-ol was procured from Merck, India, and 2,2',2''-terpyridine was purchased from Aldrich. $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}_3]$ was synthesized by following a reported procedure⁴. Tetrabutylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBHP), obtained from Aldrich, and AR grade acetonitrile, procured from Merck, India, were used for electrochemical work. All other chemicals and solvents were reagent grade commercial materials and were used as received.

Syntheses of complexes :

fac- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$: Quinolin-8-ol (132 mg, 0.92 mmol) was dissolved in 1 : 9 aqueous-ethanol (40 mL), and triethylamine (25 mg, 0.25 mmol) was added to it followed by $[\text{Ru}(\text{trpy})\text{Cl}_3]$ (100 mg, 0.23 mmol). The mixture was then refluxed for 2 h to yield a pinkish-brown solution. The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the solid mass, thus obtained, was washed with water and dried in a desiccator. The dried mass was washed further with hexane, and air dried. The crude product was purified by recrystallization from an acetonitrile-dichloromethane (1 : 1) solution, whereby the *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ complex was obtained as a brown crystalline solid. Yield : 67%; Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Ru}$: C, 60.78; H, 3.38; N, 7.88. Found : C, 60.83; H, 3.39; N, 7.93%. E. Spec data in dichloromethane solution (λ , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$)) : 1652 (240), 564 (3300), 430 (6300), 325 (10500), 314 (10200), 253 (29400).

mer- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$: *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ (100 mg) was taken up in *ortho*-xylene (100 mL) and the solution was refluxed for 10 h. Upon evaporation of the solvent under reduced pressure *mer*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ was obtained as a microcrystalline brown solid. Yield : quantitative.

Physical measurements :

Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 elemental analyzer. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a Sherwood MK-1 balance. IR spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrometer with samples prepared as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-570 spectrophotometer. ESR spectrum was recorded with a JEOL

JES-FA200 X-band spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar for measurements at 77 K (liquid dinitrogen). The ESR spectrum was calibrated with an aid of DPPH ($g = 2.0037$). Electrochemical measurements were made using a CH Instruments model 600A electrochemical analyzer. A platinum disc working electrode, a platinum wire auxiliary electrode and an aqueous saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) were used in the cyclic voltammetry experiments. All electrochemical experiments were performed under a dinitrogen atmosphere. All electrochemical data were collected at 298 K and are uncorrected for junction potentials. Optimization of ground-state structures and energy calculations for all the complexes were carried out by density functional theory (DFT) method using the Gaussian 03 (B3LYP/SDD-6-31G) package⁵.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystals of *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ were obtained by slow evaporation of solvents from a solution of the complex in acetonitrile-dichloromethane (1 : 1). Selected crystal data and data collection parameters are given in Table 1. Data

Table 1. Crystallographic data for the *fac*- $[\text{Ru}(\text{Q})_3]$ complex

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{O}_3\text{Ru}$
Formula mass	533.07
Crystal system	Trigonal
Space group	$P\bar{3}$
<i>a</i> (Å)	14.846(6)
<i>b</i> (Å)	14.846(6)
<i>c</i> (Å)	6.206(3)
α (deg)	90
β (deg)	90
γ (deg)	120
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	1184.6(9)
<i>Z</i>	2
<i>D</i> _{calcd} (mg m ⁻³)	1.547
<i>F</i> (000)	556
Crystal size (mm)	0.22 × 0.15 × 0.11
<i>T</i> (K)	298
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.699
<i>R</i> ₁ ^a	0.0903
<i>wR</i> ₂ ^b	0.2439
GOF ^c	1.32

$$^a R_1 = \frac{\sum ||F_o| - |F_c||}{\sum |F_o|}$$

$$^b wR_2 = \frac{[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / \sum [w(F_o^2)^2]]^{1/2}}$$

$$^c \text{GOF} = \frac{[\sum [w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2] / (M - N)]^{1/2}}{M}, \text{ where } M \text{ is the number of reflections and } N \text{ is the number of parameters refined.}$$

Fig. 2. DFT optimized structures of the *fac*- and *mer*-isomer of the [Ru(Q)₃] complex, and the energy difference between them.

calculations show that the *mer*-isomer is indeed more stable than the *fac*-isomer by 188 kcal/mol (Fig. 2). To examine the feasibility of converting the *fac*-isomer into the thermodynamically more stable *mer*-isomer, the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex was taken up in a high-boiling solvent, viz. *ortho*-xylene (boiling point 144° C), and refluxed for several hours. This thermal treatment has been found to transform *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] quantitatively to *mer*-[Ru(Q)₃], which has been identified by its characteristic electronic spectrum^{7d}.

Spectral studies :

Magnetic susceptibility measurement shows that the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex is one-electron paramagnetic (μ_{eff}

= 1.94 μ_{B}), which corresponds to the +3 state of ruthenium (low-spin d^5 , $S = 1/2$) in this complex. ESR spectrum of the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex has been recorded in 1 : 1 dichloromethane-toluene solution at 77 K. The spectrum, shown in Fig. 3, is found to be rhombic in nature showing three distinct signals ($g_1 = 2.406$, $g_2 = 2.156$ and $g_3 = 1.802$). The rhombicity of the spectrum reflects the asymmetry of the electronic environment around ruthenium in this *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex. The spectrum may be considered as pseudo-axial, consisting of a rather isolated signal (g_3 ; g_{\parallel} in the axial case) and two relatively close signals (g_1 and g_2 ; rhombic component of g_{\perp}). Accordingly, the axial distortion (Δ) that splits the t_2 level into a and e components is expected to be larger than the

Fig. 3. ESR spectrum of *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] in 1 : 1 dichloromethane-toluene solution at 77 K. The rhombic splitting pattern of the *t*₂-orbitals is illustrated in the inset.

rhombic distortion (*V*), which splits *e* (Fig. 3). Spin-orbit coupling causes further changes in the energy gaps. Thus, two electronic transitions (transition energies ΔE_1 and ΔE_2 ; $\Delta E_1 < \Delta E_2$) are probable within these three levels. All these energy parameters have been computed using the observed *g* values, the *g*-tensor theory of low-spin *d*⁵ complexes⁸, and a reported method⁹. The axial distortion is indeed observed to be stronger than the rhombic one ($\Delta = 4340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $V = 2490 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)¹⁰. The calculated val-

ues of ΔE_1 (3250 cm^{-1}) and ΔE_2 (5850 cm^{-1}) indicate that two ligand-field transitions should take place around 3080 nm and 1710 nm, respectively. The higher energy transition has indeed been observed in the spectrum of this complex as a rather weak and broad band at 1652 nm (*vide infra*). However, the lower energy transition could not be traced due to limitation of the equipment. The ESR spectral data thus show that the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex is significantly distorted from the ideal octahedral geometry, as was also indicated by its crystal structure.

Infrared spectrum of the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex shows many bands of different intensities in the 400–4000 cm^{-1} region. No attempt has been made to assign each individual band to a specific vibration. However, comparison with the spectrum of the corresponding uncoordinated quinolin-8-ol ligand shows that the O–H stretch, observed at 3150 cm^{-1} in the uncoordinated ligand, is absent in the complex. Besides, a sharp and strong band displayed at 1107 cm^{-1} by the complex is attributable to the C–O stretch.

The *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex is found to be readily soluble in dichloromethane, chloroform, acetonitrile, etc., producing brown solutions. Electronic spectrum of this complex has been recorded in dichloromethane solution. Spectral data are presented in the experimental section, and the spectrum is shown in Fig. 4. The *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] com-

Fig. 4. Electronic spectrum of *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] in dichloromethane solution (concentration $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$). For the inset spectrum concentration of the solution was $7.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.

plex shows several intense absorptions in the near-infrared, visible and ultraviolet regions. Origin of the weak absorption at 1652 nm has already been discussed in connection with the discussion of ESR spectral data (*vide supra*). The absorptions in the ultraviolet region are attributable to transitions within the ligand orbitals. To have an insight into the nature of absorptions in the visible region, DFT calculations have been performed on the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex⁵. Compositions of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) and the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) are given in Table 3 and contour plots of these molecular orbitals for complex 1-OCH₃ are shown in Fig. 5. The HOMO has major (~92%) contribution from two quinolinolate ligands, with minor contribution from ruthenium. The LUMO is delocalized primarily (~98%) on one quinolinolate ligand (which had least contribution to the HOMO), with little contribution coming from the metal center. The lowest energy absorption displayed by the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex at 564 nm is therefore assignable to a transition taking place from a filled quinolinolate-based orbital (HOMO) to a vacant quinolinolate-based orbital (LUMO).

Table 3. Composition of selected molecular orbitals of the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex

Contributing fragments ^a	%Contribution to	
	HOMO	LUMO
Ru	6.69	1.29
Q ¹	0.88	98.29
Q ²	44.40	0.24
Q ³	48.03	0.18

^aQ¹, Q² and Q³ depict the three chelated quinolin-8-olate ligands.

Electrochemical properties :

Electrochemical properties of the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex have been studied by cyclic voltammetry in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP). The complex shows an oxidative response at 1.11 V vs SCE and a reductive response at -0.25 V vs SCE. The voltammogram is shown in Fig. 6. Both the responses are found to be irreversible in nature. In view of composition of the HOMO in this complex, the oxidative response is assigned to oxidation of coordinated quinolinolate ligand. Similarly, based on the composition of the LUMO, the reduction is assigned

Fig. 5. Contour plot of the HOMO and LUMO of the *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex.

Fig. 6. Cyclic voltammogram of *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] in acetonitrile solution (0.1 M TBHP) at a scan rate of 50 mV s⁻¹.

to reduction of the coordinated quinolinolate ligand. It is interesting to note that potentials of the redox responses

in this *fac*-[Ru(Q)₃] differ significantly that those in the *mer*-[Ru(Q)₃] complex^{7d}.

Conclusion :

The present study shows that the facial isomer of tris(quinolin-8-olato)ruthenium(III) complex can be obtained as a kinetically controlled product from a reaction of four-fold excess of quinolin-8-ol with [Ru(trpy)Cl₃] in refluxing aqueous-ethanol (1 : 9) in the presence of a base (NEt₃). This study also demonstrates that conversion of this uncommon facial isomer of the [Ru(Q)₃] complex to the corresponding meridional isomer, which is thermodynamically more stable and is the preferred isomer for tris-chelated ruthenium(III), is possible by simple thermal agitation in refluxing *ortho*-xylene.

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Supplementary data :

Crystallographic data have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center, CCDC number 869506.

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10. The spin-orbit coupling constant (λ) is taken to be 1000 cm^{-1} for complexed ruthenium(III)⁹.